

EVALUATION FORM (VERSION 2)

Name: _____

Instructions:

1. The model to be evaluated, is available at this link:
<http://www.gabriellacastro.com.br/provswprocess/v2.html>
2. For each of the questions, we ask that one of the following be chosen:
 - *Yes*
 - *I don't know / I am not sure*
 - *No*If the option '*Yes*' is chosen, we would like to receive some justification in order to analyze the problem and try to improve the proposed model.
3. Any comments regarding the evaluation or other comments about the model should be kept at the end of this form.

Thank you.

A. Software Process Associations

A *Software Process* represents a software development process in its entirety and has the following associations: *wasAttributedTo* and *wasComposedBy* to capture retrospective provenance and the associations *hasResponsible* and *isComposedBy* to capture prospective provenance.

A-Q1) Is some association needed to describe a performed software process (in addition to *wasAttributedTo* and *wasComposedBy*) omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

A-Q2) Is some association needed to describe the prospective provenance of a software process (in addition to *hasResponsible* and *isComposedBy*) omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

A-Q3) Is some software process association not compliant with software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

A-Q4) Has some software process association the same semantic meaning (are duplicated in the model)?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

A-Q5) Is some software process association not clearly described, using ambiguous terms?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

A-Q6) Does some software process association not belong to the provenance of software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

B. Activity Associations

An Activity represents a computational task in the software development process. It can be atomic or composed by other sub-activities and may include the adoption of procedures, the use of resources, the modification, use and generation of artifacts, and the association with stakeholders responsible for its execution.

B-Q1) Is some association needed to describe the activities that were performed in a software development process (in addition to *adopted, changed, generated, used, wasAssociatedWith, wasInformedBy, wasSubActivity, startedAtTime, and endedAtTime*) omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

B-Q2) Is some association needed to describe the activities to be executed in a software development process (in addition to *adopts, changes, generates, isAssociatedWith, isSubActivity, precedes,* and *uses*) omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

B-Q3) Is some activity association not compliant with software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

B-Q4) Has some activity association the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model)?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

B-Q5) Is some activity association not clearly described, using ambiguous terms?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

B-Q6) Does some activity association not belong to the provenance of software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

C. Stakeholder Associations

A Stakeholder represents an agent involved, interested, or affected by the software process activities. It can be specialized in other three types: (i) Organization Stakeholder, (ii) Person Stakeholder, and (iii) Team Stakeholder.

C-Q1) Is some association needed to describe the relations occurred between stakeholders and other software development process constructs (in addition to *actedOnBehalfOf*, *created*, *modified*, and *hadRole*) omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification:_____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

C-Q2) Is some association needed to describe the planned relations to occur between stakeholders and other software development process constructs (in addition to *actsOnBehalfOf* and *hasRole*) omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification:_____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

C-Q3) Is the stakeholder association not compliant with software development process?

Yes –

Justification:_____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

C-Q4) Has the stakeholder association the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model) of another model association?

Yes –

Justification:_____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

C-Q5) Is the stakeholder association not clearly described, using ambiguous terms?

Yes –

Justification:_____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

C-Q6) Does the stakeholder association not belong to the provenance of software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

D. Artifact Associations

Artifacts represent the objects produced, changed, or used in the software development process activities. Artifacts can be of five types: (i) *Software_Product*, (ii) *Software_Item*, (iii) *Document*, (iv) *Model*, and (v) *Information_Item*.

D-Q1) Is some occurred association whose origin is a software process artifact (in addition to *wasBasedOn*, *wasDerivedFrom*, *generatedAtTime*, and *invalidatedAtTime*) omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

D-Q2) Is some artifact association not compliant with software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

D-Q3) Has some artifact association the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model)?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

D-Q4) Is some artifact association not clearly described, using ambiguous terms?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

D-Q5) Does some artifact association not belong to the provenance of software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

E. Procedure Association

Procedures represent a normative description prescribing a defined way for performing the software development process activities. It can be of three types: (i) Method, (ii) Document Template, and (iii) Technique.

E-Q1) Is some occurred association whose origin is a procedure (in addition to *wasAppliedTo*) omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

E-Q2) Is the procedure association not compliant with software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

E-Q3) Has the procedure association the same semantic meaning as other association (is duplicated in the model)?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

E-Q4) Is the procedure association not clearly described, using ambiguous terms?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

E-Q5) Do the procedure association not belong to the provenance of software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

F. Classes

PROV-SwProcess has 20 classes to represent the provenance of software development process. These classes are divided into five specific aspects, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. PROV-SwProcess Classes

PROV-SwProcess Aspect	Class Name
Activity	Activity
	Software_Process
Stakeholder	Stakeholder
	Organization_Stakeholder
	Person_Stakeholder
	Team_Stakeholder
	Stakeholder_Role
Resource	Resource
	Software_Resource
	Hardware_Resource
Procedure	Procedure
	Method
	Document_Template
	Technique
Artifact	Artifact
	Software_Product
	Software_Item
	Document
	Model
	Information_Item

F-Q1) Is some class needed to describe the provenance of software development process (in addition to the classes in Table 1), omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

F-Q2) Is some class not compliant with software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

F-Q3) Has some class the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model)?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

F-Q4) Is some class not clearly described, using ambiguous terms?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

F-Q5) Does some class not belong to the modeling software process domain?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

G. Inferences

PROV-SwProcess has seven groups of inferences (fifteen inference rules in total). An inference as a rule that can be applied to PROV-SwProcess instances to add new PROV-SwProcess statements.

G-Q1) Is some inference rule needed to describe the provenance of software development process omitted from the model?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

G-Q2) Is some inference rule not compliant with software development process?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

G-Q3) Has some inference rule the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model)?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

G-Q4) Is some inference rule is not clearly described, using ambiguous terms?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

G-Q5) Does some inference rule not belong to the modeling software process domain?

Yes –

Justification: _____

I don't know / I am not sure

No

General comments about the model:

General comments about the evaluation:
